

VIRUSALOGIC INDICATIONS OF SERUM FROM THE CALIFORNIA RED WORM

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ABSTRACT

Physiological research on the California red worm was carried out based on methods of research samples obtained in laboratory conditions at a high coefficient level. California red worm serum samples were collected from ten patients based on whole blood analysis. It was found out that the virological examination of two patients' blood analysis was 4.7 levels, and the blood analysis of eight patients gave 5.2 - 5.4 levels. It was analyzed that the virological component is higher in patients. The analysis of leukocytes was high, the serum of California red worm was used for the property of defeating the virus, and immunological prohibition was carried out. The immunological research solution was centrifuged from the blood fluid coming out of the lymph nodes in the body, and it was found that by applying the reagents to the patient's blood, a positive analysis of the virological research work could be performed with a high result.

When we look at the physiological pathological processes of the reparative feature in worms, we can see high quality in the treatment of infectious diseases, even the somatic of human internal organs can be affected. A unique measure is being developed for the administration of liquids to the human body.

Manure, weeds, leaves, tree branches, sawdust, straw, kitchen waste, laundry, aviary, animal waste, paper cardboard, etc.

are worm food. Nevertheless, it is necessary to collect manure and sprinkle water for 4-5 days. It is necessary to sprinkle water three times a day in southern regions in hot countries. As a result, the organic matter heats up and decomposes. It is appropriate if the biomass pile is dusted with chalk powder, slaked lime or dolomite flour. Because worms do not like a bitter environment. Worms can be fed both indoors and

outdoors. Worms can be fed in seats up to 30-100 thousand.

One ton of humus can be prepared in one seat (2x1m) in a year. 40% of nutritious substrate is used for the life of worms, 60% of biohumus is formed in the form of copromite. close worm biomass is obtained. Seats are built on slightly sloping plots so that rain does not collect and form puddles. It is important to protect the worm especially from bats, they are a fierce enemy.

It doesn't matter what day or month you start worming. The best time is spring, autumn and summer. Worms are sensitive to ammonia and high temperature. For this reason, only fermented and cooled manure can be used for feeding. Other organic waste must also rot.

A domestic rabbit is ready for worm feeding in the last 5-10 days, a horse in 3-4 months, and a cattle after 5-6 months. If there is little food, the worms will die, if there is a lot of food, breathing and gas exchange will be difficult. Always monitor the reproduction and development of worms. should be done. Worms in boxes, balcony. The land is full, it is also possible to build in garages.

Our experimental area is "Chep" and "Guliston" neighborhoods of Oltinsoy district. Simultaneously with the cultivation of nutrient-rich biohumus, the California red worm, which is used for human diseases, is isolated, fixed, filtered and placed in a drying cabinet. after drying in the oven for 48 hours, the red worm is sifted through a special tool and turned into flour. 12 mg of this sample is taken and placed in a flask, the necessary reagents are added to it and placed in a thermostat. Blood fluid obtained from the gelment is added to the gelment liquid, which is

sterilized in the thermostat, and it is centrifuged.

The serum obtained from this sample is subjected to an immunological examination and the level of influence on the human immune system is studied. The basis of this experiment was that we can see that the anti-serum is ready for 11 different diseases in the fight against human diseases and observe the pathological signs. This serum "NURZAM" is the most powerful tool for preventing hepatitis-A and hepatitis-B infection in the prevention of viral infectious diseases.

"AZAMZAR" cream ointment was prepared in a laboratory method from a sample taken from the California red worm and is used to prevent skin diseases such as leishmaniasis, vitiligo, psoriasis, and allergic rashes. Hematological indicators have been proven to be 15% higher than statistical data. It became known that the formation of erythrocytes and increase in cellularity in the human organism is regularly high

Experience shows that with the help of earthworms, it is necessary to turn organic substances into biohumus, which can be quickly absorbed by plants. Biohumus contains ten times more plant nutrients. Let's say that if 500 cattle are kept in a livestock farm, the manure produced from them can feed 200 hectares of land. This amount of organic biohumus can be used to feed 1000 hectares. 2 years ago in the "Chep" and "Guliston" neighborhoods of Oltinsoy district, pilot experiments were carried out.

Summary: The serum obtained from the California red worm is very useful for skin diseases, it helps to overcome viruses in the body, it prevents the infection of viruses, and practical work is carried out

on the basis of high-tech production equipment. Several experiments are being conducted in this regard. In the

Surkhandarya region, it is important to prevent skin rashes.

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